

Finance, business and Cultural Cold War: exploring transatlantic associationism's networks in post-war Italy

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In figure 1, we observe a bimodal network connecting some transatlantic and US cultural associations with the individuals who had formally joined them or who have participated to their activities as guests. The reference time span covers over a decade, from 1945 to 1956. This visualization is extracted from my doctoral thesis and serves as the starting point for my current post-doctoral research.

Figure 1. The graph shows a bimodal network. Green nodes correspond to associations, pink nodes correspond to individuals. Green arcs show a relation of membership between individuals and organizations, pink arcs show a relation of less formal participation to the associations' activities.

The dissertation was aimed to reconstruct the evolution of the relationship between the CIA Director Allen Dulles and the Italian Alfredo Pizzoni, President of the Credito Italiano Bank, since their collaboration during World War II when Dulles was still an agent of the CIA's predecessor, the OSS. (Piffer, 2005). The research conducted demonstrated that one area where Pizzoni and Dulles' relationship evolved was transatlantic associationism.

I therefore reconstructed such social context of transatlantic associationism that Pizzoni and Dulles shared, using associations' rosters. Thanks to the network visualization here shared, I could realize that even only focusing on a selected number of private cultural institutes and associations, plenty of intersections among people who gravitated around them emerge. Key figures who were particularly active in such environment are immediately highlighted by the graph's algorithm, opening the way to an undetected research path.

Such path is the one taken in my post-doctoral research, where I am exploring the connections between transatlantic associations and private cultural institutes active in Italy in the 1950s. My particular focus is on

the involvement of prominent figures in the Italian finance and business world within the realm of transatlantic associationism. Drawing from personal papers, such as those of Pizzoni, it becomes possible to reconstruct networks of associations like the World Brotherhood (WB in the graph), in the absence of a dedicated archive. Other key figures in this project include Arnaldo Mondadori, a significant publisher actively involved in building transatlantic ties, particularly with U.S. publisher Henri Luce, husband of the then-U.S. Ambassador to Italy, Clare Booth Luce, and Adriano Olivetti, founder of the eponymous company—one of the most significant in Italy at the time. (Decleva, 2021). Network analysis serves as a crucial methodology to reconstruct their involvement in associationism and identify ties within this panorama.

In connection with the conference's central theme, I will delve into how visualizations will be essential tools in my research to concretize considerations that would otherwise remain abstract and vague. (Grandjean, 2017; Kerschbaumer, Stark, Düring, 2020).

References

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